

**BLOOD COAGULATION DISORDERS AS A CAUSE OF JUVENILE
UTERINE BLEEDING IN ADOLESCENT GIRLS**

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Relevance. *Juvenile uterine bleeding is a serious problem in pediatric gynecology. More than half of the cases of delayed menstrual cycle in puberty end in bleeding. The frequency of the nosology in the structure of gynecological diseases ranges from 10 to 37.5%. However, the true prevalence of juvenile uterine bleeding is much higher, since the condition is very often hidden by the girl herself or underestimated by her parents. Many people generally consider bleeding during the period of formation of the menstrual cycle to be normal. This opinion is not only erroneous, but also extremely dangerous.*

Key words: *adolescent girls, juvenile uterine bleeding, blood clotting, hormonal status, diagnostics. Every year, up to 5–10% of the female population of childbearing age seeks medical help due to menorrhagia [1].*

Among all the causes of menorrhagia in women of childbearing age, blood clotting disorders account for up to 20%, of which von Willebrand factor pathology dominates in more than 80% of cases [2].

Platelet dysfunction and thrombocytopenia, afibrinogenemia or dysfibrinogenemia, deficiency of coagulation factors II, V, VII, X, XI, XIII [3–6] constitute a category of rare disorders and occur in less than 20% of cases. The first clinical manifestations of uterine bleeding in puberty manifest during the establishment of the menstrual cycle. The main causes of bleeding due to changes in blood coagulation are associated with platelet dysfunction and, most often, von Willebrand factor pathology. The functional activity of platelets and the level of von Willebrand factor depend on the general condition of the body, medication intake, physical activity, past illnesses, and the patient's blood type. The level of von Willebrand factor activity in girls can also be affected by the phase of the menstrual cycle [7].

Hormonal imbalances and associated changes in prostaglandin levels, endometrial condition, and uterine contractility can also cause hyperpolymenorrhea. A single blood coagulation test almost never reveals the cause of juvenile uterine bleeding (JUB).

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Therefore, to identify the cause of JUB, a coagulation test must be performed in parallel with a hormonal background assessment, especially in adolescent girls, taking into account the phase of the menstrual cycle. The purpose of the study is to develop an algorithm for making a diagnostic decision for laboratory detection of the cause of juvenile uterine bleeding in adolescent girls aged 12–18 years.

Material and methods We examined 30 female patients aged 12–18 years who visited the Center for Pediatric Oncology, Hematology and Immunology in the period from 2020 to 2023. Inclusion criteria for the study: prolonged (more than 7 days) and heavy periods (more than 80 ml per 1 cycle, which for sanitary and hygienic purposes requires the use of more than 3–6 pads or tampons per day), recurrent JUB [8, 9], and lack of effect from symptomatic and hormonal therapy to eliminate hyperpolymenorrhea. The presence of one of the listed signs, registered during the 12 months preceding the visit, determined the indications for inclusion in the study, assessment of the coagulation status and hormonal background on days 3–5 and 20–21 of the menstrual cycle.

Among the 30 examined adolescent girls, a mild form of von Willebrand disease type 1 was detected in 2 patients, a mild form of von Willebrand disease type 2 – in 3, severe factor VII deficiency with a baseline factor VII activity level of 1.5% – in 1 patient, hypofibrinogenemia with a baseline fibrinogen level of 0.3 g / l – in 2 patients. In 25 patients without congenital blood coagulation disorders, the level of von Willebrand factor and its activity exceeded 30%, which made it possible to consider a history of JUB, expressed to varying degrees, as a manifestation of dysfunctional uterine bleeding during the initial visit. Four of the seven patients with von Willebrand disease had a history of prolonged nosebleeds and ecchymosis, one had afibrinogenemia, and one had hypoproconvertinemia. Among the 25 adolescent girls with von Willebrand factor activity levels > 30%, 10 had a history of nosebleeds. According to parents and patients, hyperpolymenorrhea in the first phase of the cycle at the time of examination occurred in 12 of 30 patients. Menorrhagia was noted in three of the seven patients with von Willebrand disease (von Willebrand factor level and/or activity < 29 %), one patient with severe factor VII deficiency, and one girl with hypofibrinogenemia. Heavy periods were observed in 5 adolescent girls with O(I) and 1 patient with A(II) group affiliation, in whom the level of von Willebrand factor varied from 30 to 40%. Complaints of hyperpolymenorrhea were also presented by 7 patients with the level of von Willebrand factor over 40%. At the time of the study, 17 adolescent girls had a history of irregular and heavy periods over the previous year. Of the 25 patients without congenital or acquired coagulation disorders, examined in the first phase of the cycle (3rd–5th day), 2 groups were formed.

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The first group consisted of 7 adolescent girls who had hyperpolymenorrhea at the time of the study. The 2nd group included 14 patients who had irregular and heavy periods in their anamnesis during the previous year, without signs of hyperpolymenorrhea at the time of the study.

The control group included 15 somatically healthy adolescent girls of the same age without manifestations of hyperpolymenorrhea at the time of the study (3rd-5th day of the cycle) - two of them noted nosebleeds, periodically occurring for 5 minutes. All patients and their parents signed informed consent for participation in the study of hormonal status and blood clotting. According to the parents and the adolescent girls themselves, during the last 2 weeks preceding the study, they did not take medications that could directly or indirectly affect blood clotting and platelet function. The blood coagulation study included the determination of chronometric and structural parameters using automatic coagulometers ACL-200 and ACL9000 (Instrumentation Laboratory, IL) using diagnostic kits from IL. Activated partial thromboplastin time (APTT) was recorded according to Caen; prothrombin time according to Quick with calculation of the activity of prothrombin complex factors and the international normalized ratio taking into account the sensitivity of thromboplastin; thrombin time according to Biggs, Macfarlane; the content of plasma fibrinogen coagulated by thrombin, by the Clauss method. The activity of factors VIII and IX was recorded in all patients using the one-stage clotting method, and if it was necessary to clarify the diagnosis, the activity of factors II, V, VII, X, XI, XII was determined. The level of a protein with the properties of the von Willebrand factor antigen (AgvWF) and ristocetin cofactor activity (functional activity) of the von Willebrand factor (vWF:RCo) were recorded. Both indicators were determined by the turbidimetric method on an ACL-9000 coagulometer (USA) using diagnostic kits from Instrumentation Laboratory. For coagulation parameters, normal control plasma included in the diagnostic kits of Instrumentation Laboratory was used as a control. Laboratory. The peripheral blood platelet count was performed using the MICROS-60 automatic analyzer. The platelet aggregation activity was recorded using the turbidimetric method on the AR 2110 SOLAR optical aggregometer. Ristocetin (Ristocetin) manufactured by Diagnostica was used as an inducer. Stago / Roche at a final concentration of 1 mg / ml. Immunoenzyme photochemiluminescence method on the Cobas e 411 analyzer from Roche Hitachi using original Roche reagents Hitachi determined the content of progesterone, testosterone, follicle-stimulating hormone, prolactin and cortisol. Blood group was determined for all patients. Statistical analysis of the data was performed using the Statistica software package (version 6.0). Quantitative indicators of descriptive statistics are presented as the mean and values $\pm 95\%$ confidence interval.

The reliability of differences in indicators in the compared groups was estimated using the Mann-Whitney criterion. To identify the relationship between the fact of bleeding, on the one hand, and the state of blood clotting and hormonal status, on the other hand, nonparametric methods of correlation analysis with determination of the correlation coefficient G were used.

Specificity and sensitivity of laboratory indicators used to identify the cause of JUB were estimated by constructing characteristic curves using the ROC analysis method. To determine the diagnostic threshold of the most significant indicators and develop a diagnostic algorithm, the method of constructing a classification tree for making a diagnostic decision was used.

Conclusion. Thus, every 5th adolescent girl aged 12–18 years with a history of recurrent uterine bleeding had hyperpolymenorrhea at the time of examination in the first phase of the cycle.

To identify the cause of JUB in adolescent girls, in addition to routine laboratory tests, it is necessary to determine the activity of von Willebrand factor, progesterone and testosterone levels in the blood. A 2–3-fold decrease in the progesterone level compared to the control was accompanied by hyperpolymenorrhea in 7 of 15 adolescent girls, indicating a dysfunctional nature of bleeding. The diagnostic range of von Willebrand factor activity and content, within which hyperpolymenorrhea is considered a clinical sign of "latent disorders" of coagulation, should be expanded to 35% for patients with O(I) group affiliation and to 38% for patients with A(II), B(III) and AB(IV) group affiliation.

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